

Cyanobacteria : A neglected potent candidate for biodiesel production

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Abstract : Algae have emerged as a potent biofuel resource due to the presence of triacylglycerol. Fatty acids esters of appropriate chain length are used as biodiesels. Cyanobacteria are devoid of triacylglycerol, consequently are not considered as biodiesel resource. However, emphasis is not given on other fatty acid containing lipids like phospholipid, glycolipid, and steryl esters of cyanobacteria. In the present study two cyanobacteria i.e. *Anabaena anomala*, *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and one macroalga *Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum* respectively were lysed and lipid was extracted separately. The maximum quantity of total lipid was available from macroalgal biomass followed by two cyanobacteria. We have compared lipid and fatty acid compositions of two cyanobacteria with macroalga. Triacylglycerol and steryl ester were major neutral lipid in macroalga. Triacylglycerol on hydrolysis produces three fatty acids per molecule. The cyanobacteria provided reasonable amount of glycolipid and phospholipid which can deliver two fatty acids against each molecule, while steryl ester can contribute one. In this article, we attempt to accentuate that cyanobacteria should be considered as a significant resource of biodiesel as it contains fatty acids of suitable chain length in appreciable quantity.

Keywords : Biodiesel, cyanobacteria, macroalga, fatty acid, transesterification.

Introduction

Biodiesel is usually produced from oleaginous source. Biodiesel production from microalgae is a relatively novel concept and these organisms offer the greatest photosynthetic efficiency, as a consequence of third generation biofuels derived from algal and microalgal biomass are considered to be a worthwhile alternative energy resource, also they are devoid of the major drawbacks associated with first and second generation biofuels^{1,2}. Many species of microalgae are described as oleaginous due to their capacity to yield substantial amounts of intracellular lipids that can be transformed to biodiesel. They have oil content in the range of 20–50% dry weight of biomass³. In both algae and cyanobacteria, amount of lipid varies with species^{4,5}. Cyanobacteria possess certain prop-

erties which have entitled them to be one of the most promising feed stocks for bioenergy generation as they can contain considerable amounts of lipids and can act as a promising model to transform all the C sources into valuable fuels like ethanol, oil and biogas⁶. Generally, species containing high amount of triacylglycerols (TAG) are considered as good source for biodiesel. The hydrogenation of TAG produces a pure hydrocarbon chain (paraffin) which is devoid of oxygen but slight amounts of water, while CO₂ and propane are by-products⁷. However, the development of processes for conversion of algal lipid to biodiesel to achieve cost efficiencies that rival petroleum based fuels is an on-going challenge that demands in-depth understanding of lipid structure along with algal biology and process engineering. As candidate for biofuel-

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producing microbial biomass, cyanobacteria have favourable characteristics. For example growth rate compared to other energy crops, higher photosynthetic efficiency, higher biomass production, simple input requirements, tolerance of marginal agricultural environments, more amenable to genetic manipulation for increasing biofuel, and carbon-neutral applications and biodiesel production. These aspects of cyanobacteria had combined to capture the interest of researchers and entrepreneurs. Analysis of cyanobacterial species had shown remarkable difference in lipid content among different biomass, ranging from 1% to approximately 85% of dry cell weight⁸ with different proportions of total, neutral, glyco and phospholipids.

As percentage of TAG in most of the cyanobacterial neutral lipid (NL) has been found to be negligible, this class of microalgae has been discarded by many researchers for biodiesel production⁹. Cyanobacteria contain many lipid classes other than TAG which have fatty acids (FAs) in esterified form like steryl esters, glycolipid (GL) and phospholipid (PL)¹⁰. Such lipids on transesterification with methanol are capable of forming fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) and can be used as biodiesel. In addition to the proficient recovery of TAGs, the ability to recover other lipids may be of great importance in producing better quality product that can improve the larger-scale biofuel production processes¹¹. Therefore, suitability of any algae for biodiesel resource should not solely depend on its amount of TAG but on the amount of fatty acid containing lipids and nature of the fatty acids (chain length and unsaturation). For the production of lipid-based biofuels, cyanobacteria have not attained much of attention than other feed stocks⁸. For economic biodiesel production; residual algae biomass plays an important role. Simultaneously other natural resource of same kingdom like macroalgal cell biomass might be considered for lipid analysis because fresh water filamentous algae are ubiquitous globally and it has various combinations of saturated as well as unsaturated fatty acid

apart from TAG which could be further processed for biodiesel production¹².

The present study therefore directed towards exploring and comparing the abundance and composition of lipid from cyanobacterial and macroalgal biomass which can further serve as a prospective resource for biofuel. A number of researches had been carried out with analysing lipid of cyanobacteria but no comparison has been made between macroalgae and cyanobacteria especially with respect to their lipid, fatty acid measure and its prospect for biodiesel production. Here we have studied the relative amount of different lipid classes in two cyanobacterial biomass i.e. *Anabaena anomala* and *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and a macroalgal biomass *Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum*. For the said purpose total lipid was extracted from dry biomass of each sample, after rupturing the cells by two different lysis procedures i.e. grinding by mortar-pestle and sonication. Since cell wall and membrane present in algae are formidable barriers to permeation by extraction solvents, cells have to be disrupted prior to extraction which enhances oil recovery. In our previous study, different cell lysis methods had been applied before lipid extraction from cyanobacteria but the said methods were found to be most effective¹³. Detailed lipid analysis was carried out chromatographically to identify the FA containing lipids and the FA of each component were analysed after converting them into FAME. So, it is needless to mention that although biodiesel seems currently economically viable from algal triacylglycerol but other sources of fatty acid from neutral, glyco and phospholipids had never been emphasized earlier where lies the novelty of our work. Further a comparison was made to find out the algal species with high oil contents and biodiesel production efficacy.

Experimental

Chemicals :

All the chemicals were of AR grade and purchased from Merck. Lipid standards were procured from Sigma. Others are mentioned in the text.

Algal sampling and identification :

All the algal samples used in this study were identified from Botanical Survey of India, Ministry of Environment & Forests, Kolkata, India. The two cyanobacteria i.e. *Anabaena anomala* (Aa) and *Oscillatoria subbrevis* (Os) were collected individually from East Kolkata Wetland, West Bengal. East Kolkata Wetland, a Ramsar site of International Importance is an example of diversified flora and fauna enriched region¹⁴. The cyanobacterial strains were cultivated in BG-11 media. Both of these strains were incubated at 25 ± 2 °C with continuous illumination by natural light during day and artificial source (2400 lux) after sunset¹⁵ and cultured in the media for two weeks and sub cultured with fresh autoclaved media thereafter. The cyanobacterial cells were harvested by vacuum filtration, and the wet cell biomass was dried at 60 °C overnight in a hot air oven. The dry biomass was determined gravimetrically. A freshwater green macroalga *Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum* (Rh) was collected from Durgapur, West Bengal and processed for lipid extraction directly as continuous supply was available. It was collected during the dry season (November-March), when it was reported to exhibit maximum growth¹⁶.

Cell disruption :

The wet biomass (dry biomass soaked in distilled water) were disrupted using two different methods namely, grinding by mortar-pestle and by sonication using Microson Ultrasonic Cell Disruptor at a resonance of 10 KHz for 10 min, to identify the more effective one for cell disruption.

Lipid fractionation and analysis :

After cell disruption, the total lipid (TL) was extracted from all the samples by Bligh & Dyer method¹⁷. Subsequently the lipid containing organic solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. The weight of the lipid was determined gravimetrically. The total lipid obtained from all the three biomass were fractionated separately by col-

umn chromatography using silica (60–120 mesh)¹⁸.

The NL, GL and PL fractions were obtained sequentially using chloroform, acetone and methanol¹⁸. Thin layer chromatography was performed on Merck 60 F254 silica plates for further fractionating the different components of NL and PL against appropriate standards. Hexane : ether : acetic acid (7 : 3 : 0.5 v/v/v) and triethylamine : chloroform : ethanol : water : (7 : 6 : 5 : 1.4 v/v/v/v) were used as mobile phase for separation of NL and PL components respectively. Triolene, sterol, steryl ester, wax ester and hydrocarbon for NL and phosphatidyl serine, phosphatidyl inositol, phosphatidyl ethanolamine, phosphatidyl choline and sphingomyelin for PL were used as markers.

Transesterification of fatty acid :

The extracted total lipid and its fractions namely, NL, GL and PL were transesterified into fatty acid methyl ester as conducted in our earlier work¹³. FAMES were purified by TLC against methyl pentadecanoate before analysing by gas chromatography.

FAME analysis by gas chromatography :

FAMES were identified and quantified by gas chromatograph (Agilent 7820A) using a method described earlier¹³.

Statistical analysis :

All results are expressed in Mean \pm SD of three experiments. Student's t test was carried out to find out whether the changes were significant ($p < 0.05$ was considered significant).

Results and discussion

Lipid analysis of cyanobacteria and alga :

From dried biomass of *Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum*, 29.06 and 17.03% of total lipid was obtained while 25.89 and 13.87% of total lipid was obtained from *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and finally 21.98 and 15.01% of total lipid was obtained from *Anabaena anomala* when lysed by mortar-pestle and probe sonication methods, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1. Total lipid (as % of dry biomass) from three strains by mortar-pestle and sonication method

Cell disruption method	<i>Anabaena anomala</i>	<i>Oscillatoria subbrevis</i>	<i>Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum</i>
Mortar-pestle	21.98±0.57	25.89±1.03	29.06±0.05
Sonication	15.01±0.24	13.87±0.78	17.03±0.25

Extracted total lipid from each strain were fractionated into NL, GL and PL as shown in Fig. 1. With mortar-pestle method highest amount of NL was found from Rh (68.04% of TL) followed Aa (63.64%) and Os (61.14%). On the contrary, on sonication, Os yielded maximum NL (71.18%) preceding Rh (63.91%) and Aa (53.10%).

The cyanobacterial strains Aa and Os produced 27.63 and 23.45% of GL by mortar-pestle method and 26.21 and 21.66% by sonication process showing little variation between two processes. Macroalgal strain Rh produced 24.24% of GL by mortar-pestle and 23.91% by sonication method, again exhibiting insignificant variation ($p > 0.01$).

In case of PL, 15.38% was obtained from Os by mortar-pestle lysis method followed by Aa (8.63%) and Rh (7%). On the other hand, using sonication lysis different yield was obtained. Here it was observed that Aa produced 20.66% of PL followed by Rh (12.15%) and Os (7.14%).

Question naturally arises as why the same cyanobacteria or macroalga render different amount of total lipid and its components when lysed by different techniques. This may happen as algae have cell wall which does not disrupt uniformly when subjected to different types of lysis processes¹⁹. NLs are mainly located in the cytosolic part of algal cells in the form of TAG while PL and GL are integral part of cell membrane²⁰. Thick and rigid cell wall reduces the penetration of solvent for oil extraction, and poses a significant resistance to most of the organic solvent. On cell rupture, lipids are exposed from cellular compartments and dispersed to surrounding medium. From Fig. 1 it was evident that amount of NL and PL of all the three species were significantly different ($p < 0.01$) when they were lysed by different processes while GL amount was almost same. Higher variation was observed in case of PL. Cell membranes are mainly constituted of PL and are covered with cell wall. Thus with the specific cell lysis process, rupture the algal cell wall in partial or incomplete extent will lead to extraction of cell membrane components in varying extent. The present work, therefore, signifies the importance of proper cell disruption procedure.

It was found, macroalga Rh stood out as the most

Fig. 1. Neutral, glyco and phospholipid percentages of three algal strains expressed as percentage of total lipid of each strain.

promising one among the three biomass as it persevered highest amount of lipid producing property. As manual grinding with mortar-pestle resulted as the most effective cell disruption technique for algal species studied in the present investigation, subsequent lipid analysis was carried out by this method. Similar findings have been reported by Lee *et al.*²¹ where mechanical treatment like bead beating was more successful in extracting higher lipid content from macroalgae than sonication, homogenization, French press or lyophilisation²¹.

Further analysis of lipid component :

The NL and PL obtained from Aa, Os and Rh were further fractionated as shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2. Neutral lipid components in three algal strains

Neutral lipids ^a	<i>Anabaena anomala</i>	<i>Oscillatoria subbrevis</i>	<i>Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum</i>
Triacylglycerol	-	-	25.04±0.73
Sterol	29.40±0.59	23.75±1.08	28.03±0.14
Steryl ester	32.11±0.50	35.58±1.52	21.05±0
Wax ester	-	-	-
Hydrocarbon	-	-	-

^aExpressed as percentage of total lipid.

The result illustrated that sterol and steryl esters were found in all the strains. Cyanobacterial biomass yielded more steryl esters than macroalga, but did not contained TAG. Moreover, wax ester or hydrocarbon was neither detected in macroalga nor in cyanobacteria. Evidently the macroalga contained TAG and thus, expected to produce good quantity of biodiesel. PL fractions from all the three strains (Table

3) showed predominance of phosphatidyl serine and phosphatidyl choline. Phosphatidyl inositol could not be detected in any sample. Furthermore, no traces of phosphatidyl ethanolamine or sphingomyelin were found in Rh.

Analysis of FAME :

The FAME compositions of cyanobacteria and macroalgae have been listed in Table 4. It was observed that less amount of lauric acid (C12:0) was present in Rh than cyanobacterial strain Os. Amongst the other FAs, palmitic (C16:0) and oleic acid (C18:1) were abundant in all the three strains. The order of the major FAs obtained from Rh in the present study was C16:0, C18:3, C18:0, C18:1. The FAME analysis of total lipid also revealed negligible variation between total C16 population i.e. ($\Sigma C16 = C16:0 + C16:1$) and total C18 population i.e. ($\Sigma C18 = C18:0 + cis-C18:1 + trans-C18:1 + cis-C18:2 + trans-C18:2 + C18:3$).

In case of NL (Table 4), quantity of lauric acid was much lower in macroalgal strain unlike both of the cyanobacteria. Considerable amount of palmitic acid was obtained in all the strains, among which, Rh was found to contain maximum amount (42.6%). Besides stearic acid, substantial amount of oleic acid was present in all the three strains and the highest being in Rh (17.4%). Generally it has been reported that oil with high oleic acid content illustrates good biofuel properties²². Thus FAME of Rh can be considered as a strong alternative for the diesel replacement. Here also it was eminent that $\Sigma C16$ for Aa and Rh resembled each other.

Table 3. Phospholipid components in three algal strains

Phospholipids ^a	<i>Anabaena anomala</i>	<i>Oscillatoria subbrevis</i>	<i>Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum</i>
Phosphatidyl serine	1.13±1.90	3.75±0.16	0.3892±0
Phosphatidyl inositol	-	-	-
Phosphatidyl ethanolamine	1.75±0.57	4.17±1.28	-
Phosphatidyl choline	3.33±1.51	3.15±0.19	6.61±0
Sphingomyelin	2.27±0.34	3.73±1.19	-

^aExpressed as percentage of total lipid.

Table 4. FAME analysis of lipids from three algal strains

Fatty acids (%)	Total lipid			Neutral lipid			Glyco lipid			Phospho lipid		
	Aa ^e	Os ^b	Rh ^c	Aa ^e	Os ^b	Rh ^c	Aa ^e	Os ^b	Rh ^c	Aa ^e	Os ^b	Rh ^c
C12:0	2.38±0.43	8.87±0.24	3.67±0.06	34.27±4.28	24.59±1.65	2.16±0.53	3.77±0.07	4.37±0.04	0.61±0.02	12.47±2.04	11.58±2.54	0.45±0.03
C13:0	-	0.64±0.41	0.82±0.02	3.08±0.56	2.71±0.03	1.56±0.67	1.93±0.05	-	0.47±0.01	2.97±0.12	-	-
C14:0	8.03±1.65	2.22±0.2	0.94±0.09	17.92±3.01	19.81±1.98	3.74±0.28	1.35±0.03	4.60±1.03	8.8±1.10	2.57±0.04	7.68±2.0	6.3±1.12
C16:0	41.8±5.42	42.11±5.13	52.21±0.56	12.57±2.25	16.54±1.14	42.59±2.24	31.91±2.5	37.38±1.23	51.26±2.54	35.05±1.85	47.82±1.27	73.65±3.01
C16:1	7.44±1.13	-	2.88±0.99	4.00±0.17	3.89±0.17	2.14±0.58	16.08±1.87	15.29±1.10	0.3±0	7.12±0.04	5.71±1.12	1.53±0.24
C17:0	1.89±1.0	1.13±1.32	0.89±0.58	-	1.82±1.05	4.07±1.29	2.48±0.04	2.38±0.88	1.04±0.07	7.72±2.54	-	0.52±0
C17:1	1.38±0.02	-	2.63±0.03	8.77±1.47	8.21±1.71	-	2.16±0.99	1.44±0.07	-	5.35±0.24	4.68±1.12	0.33±0.01
C18:0	4.87±0.33	3.52±0.14	11.56±0.29	1.81±0.45	3.17±0.11	9.97±2.49	2.47±0.21	4.28±0.12	8.9±0.05	7.72±1.24	2.75±0.14	6.76±0.92
C18:1 ^{c,d}	-	21.21±3.51	-	8.33±0.14	8.81±0.24	17.4±1.76	25.06±2.24	16.08±1.13	11.35±1.23	10.87±2.15	8.27±1.45	2.75±1.35
C18:1 ^e	16.72±0.05	0.57±0.18	8.88±0.45	-	-	4.63±1.10	-	-	10.7±1.52	-	-	3.33±0.07
C18:2 ^{c,d}	11.34±4.87	19.73±2.14	-	3.67±0.02	5.94±1.12	4.14±0.96	11.9±1.23	11.25±1.08	5.44±1.05	3.80±0.2	7.36±0.75	3.04±0.41
C18:2 ^f	-	-	-	-	-	2.4±0.54	-	-	0.51±0.02	-	-	0.7±0.02
C18:3	4.15±0.89	-	15.52±1.54	5.58±0.24	4.51±0.55	1.27±2.12	0.89±0.54	2.93±0.05	0.62±0.12	4.32±1.54	4.15±0.12	0.64±0.15
SFA ^f	58.97	58.49	70.09	69.65	68.64	64.09	43.91	53.01	71.08	60.78	69.83	87.68
MUFA ^g	25.54	21.78	14.39	21.1	20.91	25.87	43.3	32.81	22.35	23.34	18.66	7.94
PUFA ^h	15.49	25.17	15.52	9.25	10.45	10.04	12.79	14.18	6.57	8.12	11.51	4.38

^aAa - *Anabaena anomala*, ^bOs - *Oscillatoria subbrevis* and ^cRh - *Rhizoctonium hieroglyphicum*; ^dc - *cis*, ^et - *trans*; ^fSFA - saturated fatty acid, ^gMUFA - mono-unsaturated fatty acid and ^hPUFA - polyunsaturated fatty acid.

FAME analysis of GL (Table 4), of all the three strains elucidated that, the quantity of lauric acid was negligible in macroalga but not so in cyanobacteria. Considerable amount of palmitic acid was produced by both of the cyanobacterial and macroalgal strain. The presence of higher amount of palmitic and stearic acid also aids the biodiesel property of Rh. On the other hand, the oleic acid content was more in case of cyanobacterial strains which can improve their biodiesel efficacy. The relative population of Σ C16 was similar for Os and Rh but Σ C18 was similar for all the strains when compared.

While analysing the FAME of PL it was revealed, both cyanobacterial strains contained much higher amount of lauric acid than the macroalga. The quantity of palmitic acid was appreciable in all the three strains with Rh producing maximum amount (73.6%). In PL, amount of oleic acid (beneficial for biodiesel characterization) in cyanobacterial sample was much greater than the macroalgal counterpart. No resemblance was found in the relative abundance of Σ C16 or Σ C18 FAs.

Overall, the FAME analysis of NL, GL and PL demonstrated notable predominance of myristic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid and oleic acid, thus characterizing the biodiesel property of the studied strains. Cyanobacteria produce a wide variety of FAs with chain length from C10 to C24 depending on species or strains. FAME with higher percentage of palmitate and oleate reflect good biofuel properties such as lubricity, quality ignition and higher oxidative stability²³. Experimental FA analysis data highlighted the presence of major proportion of saturated and mono unsaturated fatty acid making it less prone to oxidation. Earlier it had been reported that FA and FAME with four or more double bonds are vulnerable to oxidation during storage and this reduces their tolerability as biodiesel especially for vehicle use²⁴. Such polyunsaturated fatty acids were absent in the cyanobacterial and macroalgal strains studied. It was

found that FAME was mostly composed of chain length C-14 to C-18, making it prospective to be used as biodiesel.

Lipid content is a critical variable for evaluating algal species for biodiesel production. The tendency of algae to store TAG has ensured a greater attention on their potential as a raw material for biodiesel production than cyanobacteria, which characteristically store carbon as glycogen or polyhydroxyalkanoates²⁵. Moreover, accentuation had been given on strategic improvement for better yield of lipid but nevertheless had been highlighted towards the total amount of fatty acid^{26,27}. TAG is rightfully considered the best candidate for biodiesel production because each molecule has three FAs. Wax ester and steryl esters have only one FA per molecule while GL and PL have two FAs per molecule (Fig. 2). Thus while considering a macro or microalgal biomass for source of biodiesel, not only TAG but also other suitable FA containing lipid components should be taken into account. It is well documented that cyanobacteria do not contain TAG and therefore not generally considered as a good source for biodiesel²⁸. The cyanobacterial strains used in the present study also did not contain TAG but had appreciable amount of steryl ester, GLs and PLs. Per 100 g of total lipid of cyanobacterial species Aa, 32 g of steryl ester were produced (Table 2) and sum of PL and GL was found to be 36.16 g. Again, quite an appreciable amount (35%) of steryl ester was extracted by mortar-pestle method from Os. From this strain, total GL+PL obtained was 38.83% of total lipid. Therefore, cyanobacteria contain appreciable amount of FA containing lipids which may be further transesterified to produce biodiesel.

In the macroalga Rh, which produced maximum amount of TL, total percentage of GL+PL was 31.24. Its amount of steryl ester was less than cyanobacteria, but presence of TAG made it highest FA producing species among the three. Considering three FAs from

Fig. 2. Structures of different fatty acid containing lipids, (a) triacylglycerol, (b) wax ester, (c) steryl ester, (d) phospholipid and (e) glycolipid.

TAG, two from GL and PL and one from steryl ester (Fig. 2) it was calculated that Rh produced 50% more FAs than either of cyanobacteria.

These cyanobacteria though did not contain TAG, produced substantial amount of FA containing lipids viz. GL, PL and steryl ester. Also the major FA from cyanobacteria was of suitable length for biodiesel. Though the total amount of lipid from cyanobacteria is less than TAG containing macroalga it can act as alternative renewable biodiesel. Hence, along with TAG other fatty acid containing lipid should be considered for availability of total FAME so as to optimum utilization of bioresource. Many researchers had

already carried out work based on the assessment of lipid productivity of algae like Esperanza Del Rio *et al.*²⁹. However amount of total fatty acid or their chain length were not considered. The results acquired from the present investigation indicate that cyanobacteria do contain lipids available for undeviating transformation to biodiesel^{9,30}. High-rate lipid-production due to their high levels of photosynthesis and rapid growth rate also favor their renewable nature³¹.

We therefore propose that while assessing prospective bio-resource for biodiesel, not the amount of TL or TAG but the proportion of FA containing lip-

ids (along with number of FAs they produce) needs to be considered. Therefore the main interest should shift towards the availability of biodiesel from the total amount of fatty acids of algae instead of TAG. Thus being a potent candidate for biodiesel production cyanobacteria can have a profound impact on the future welfare of the planet by addressing the pressing issues of alternative energy resources.

Conclusions

In this paper we have shown the lipid and fatty acid composition of two cyanobacteria and one macroalga. The macroalga, *Rhizoclonium hieroglyphicum* contains good amount of lipid (above 25%) including TAG. Though cyanobacteria do not contain TAG, it has other lipids containing fatty acids with chain length suitable for biodiesel production. We have argued that for considering a biodiesel source, not the amount of TAG but total number of fatty acids with suitable chain length should be taken into account. Thus suitable species of cyanobacteria may also be considered as resource for biodiesel.

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